

DETERMINATION OF INTER-WELL SPACE CONDUCTIVITY USING NEW DIAGNOSTIC METHODOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Existing methods of hydrodynamic research have been analyzed, in particular methods of inter-well-bore space detection, and their main drawbacks have been determined. The article presents a new method of productive horizon detection using an electro-paramagnetic resonance signal from a magnetic com-posit containing a spinning macro hetero cycle which characterizes the presence and/or absence of cross-flow in the inter-well space of fluid injected to the drilling area through the pumping wells. The received information about the water-flooded formation state and degree of its drainage is the base for the determination of more preferable location coordinates of additional injection wells in the field development grid. The above-said studies prove the efficiency of the suggested method and are expected to contribute greatly to cost reduction while drilling the wells.

Keywords: water flooding, formation detection, electro-paramagnetic resonance, magnetic composite, inter-well flow.

Introduction

Hydrodynamic research is one of the methods of well and reservoir research, which is a complex of activities aimed at obtaining information about the composition and properties of the productive formation, both existing and abandoned or drilled wells.

The hydrodynamic method of investigation is carried out in several modes, which are noted below [1]:

- At steady-state modes (taking indicator diagrams);
- at unsteady modes (taking KVD, KPD, CWD, CWU);
- hydro-listening mode (observation of pressure change in the first well (listening well) during the change of the neighboring well operation mode).

Hydrodynamic research of wells allows determining the following well properties [7]:

- ground pressure;
- filtration coefficients;
- water and gas content of formations;
- water permeability of the productive horizon;
- distance of formation zones from the surface;
- degree of saturation of productive formations with useful resources;
- physical parameters of well products (density, volume, pressure, viscosity percentage, etc.).

Among all listed well properties, the special place is occupied by the filtration coefficient and hydraulic conductivity of inter-well sections.

It should be noted that the direct dependence of borehole hydraulic conductivity on rock porosity has been proved by many studies [1-5]. Primary (intergranular) and secondary porosity are distinguished by the nature of the formation. Primary porosity depends on the structure, properties, and roundness of downhole rock's constituent particles. Secondary porosity depends on epigenetic and tectonic processes taking place in productive strata. For example, the formation of secondary porosity due to selective dissolution of the mineral structure of rocks by formation waters, due to the formation of cracks in the structural layers of the borehole formation, etc. Therefore, all the above-mentioned processes influence the porosity of productive layers, i.e. they can both increase and decrease the porosity [6].

In addition, the composition of rocks comprising the pay zone affects the porosity of the well. It is

necessary to have a consolidated stratigraphic section for each specific location.

Within the currently used typical GIS complex, three groups of methods are used to determine the porosity of rocks [2]:

- Method of scattered gamma rays. Here is determined only the total porosity of rocks, is determined by the volumes of granular pores, caverns, cracks, and residual water in particles of clay minerals.
- Neutron method. By means of this method, by correct selection of a combination of density and selective gamma and neutron logs, it is possible to obtain complete information for lithologic separation of the pay zone section and gamma logs allow correlating logging curves with borehole depth.
- Acoustic method. Unlike other types of logging, the acoustic method is used for hydrodynamic studies of low-porosity, small-porous rocks. In rocks with caverns and cracks, the calculated porosity values are inaccurate and underestimated, and for the exact determination of porosity, it is necessary to use other logging methods. It should be noted that if acoustic measurements are sufficiently reliable, it is possible to estimate the secondary porosity of productive formation by the difference between data on medium porosity obtained by density and acoustic methods.

Rock porosity, in its turn, affects the filtration characteristics of the productive horizon. There are various ways of establishing filtration characteristics in the inter-well space of the oil reservoir.

The first method is a determination of filtration characteristics in the inter-well space of the drained oil reservoir volume according to well operation data by the speed of perturbing signal passage in the drained reservoir space between interacting injection and production wells, by the time lag of responding signal and distance between these wells [3]. The disadvantage is that it can be used to determine permeability only for water and not for gas, oil, and in areas without core material.

The second method is a determination of filtration-volumetric properties of productive strata, which consists of geophysical, hydrodynamic (at steady-state and non-steady-state filtration modes) and petrophysical well studies and by their result's construction of correlation dependence of corresponding parameters. They also determine basic porosity-volumetric reservoir parameters, optimal bottom-hole pressures during selection and injection of the reagent, put the well into the operating mode with optimal bottom-hole pressures, make hydraulic interference at the optimal bottom-hole pressures, and determine the working thickness and permeability of the working formation between injection and production wells, after that the porosity-permeability correlation shows the limiting value of porosity, that corresponds to the found limiting value [4]. The disadvantage is that their application is possible during long stops of reacting wells for the establishment of a constant pressure value, which leads to big production losses.

The third method is a determination of filtration parameters in a multilateral well system by ICG method when a three-dimensional hydrodynamic model is built and filtration reservoir parameters (hydraulic conductivity, injectivity, skin-factor, etc.) are determined by ICG method [5]. The disadvantage is that this method requires highly specialized software, which can be purchased only by a certain number of people.

Problem statement

Considering the above-mentioned and having carried out a number of investigations in the field of determination of conductivity and porosity of pay zones, we offer a technology for the detection of inter-formational fluid overflows injected into the formation through the injection wells, which can be used for:

- to estimate filtration-volumetric properties of the developed field;
 - for reservoir pressure maintenance and correction of waterflood projects;
 - to define the place of injection wells and add them to the field development grid on the route map.
- The essence of the suggested technique is to determine internal inter-well interflows by injecting fluid through the injection well into the drained reservoir space and further analyzing the production of production wells located at the wellhead.

The solution of the problem

The set task is solved in the way that flooding projects are corrected on the basis of the information received as a result of the analysis of the producing well production for the presence of the electro-paramagnetic resonance signal from the magnetic composite containing the spun macro-heterocycle characterizing the presence and/or absence of overflows in the inter-well space of the fluid injected through the injection wells into the drained part of the reservoir.

The novelty of the development lies in the fact that the fluid injected through the injection wells into the drained reservoir space prior to its pumping is treated with a specially prepared on the basis of magnetic nanocomposite containing a spinning macro-heterocycle with the required temperature Sedimentation, hydrogen, granulation, corrosion stability, and agglomeration stability indicators and at the wellhead the production wells are analyzed for the presence of the electrical vapor resonance signal (EPR) to identify the treated liquid injected into the formation space.

The proposed method of detecting within formation fluid overflows of injection wells consists in the fact that for effective implementation of wells flooding projects, a liquid suspension of magnetic nanocomposite containing spun-mixed macro-heterocycle in the proportion of 1:1000 l, treated with the addition of surfactant, corrosion inhibitor, and antifoam additive is added to the injected injection fluid. Afterward, the prepared liquid volume is pumped into the reservoir via an injection well, and after the injection, the production of the production wells is analyzed at the wellhead by EPR-spectroscopy. The signals of the production wells are used to map their interaction with the injection wells and to determine the presence of communication channels in the inter-well space of the development string and the corresponding inter-formational flow rate.

To prevent complications during water flood projects, the injection fluid is made by adding a liquid concentration of magnetic powder with the following properties:

- preparation time of the aqueous suspension of magnetic powder and heating fluid based on it - no more than 20-30 minutes;
- range of temperature application - $30 < T < 150$ °C;
- powder sedimentation - (1-1000), l/hour;
- value of hydrogen index - $\text{pH} > 10$;
- corrosion protection - within 3 months.

The labeled fluid flows are used to study hydrodynamic background and intraformational flows in the field under development. The proposed detection method consists of the following stages of implementation (see figure):

1. As a result of the continuous supply of the injection well with the given volume of fluid, the injected product subject to development is displaced to the production wells, i.e. there is a need for the presence of production and injection wells.
2. At the end of the operation, samples are taken from the production wells to determine the presence and quantitative assessment of labeled traces of fluid. For this purpose, the corresponding analyses are carried out in laboratory conditions, the results of which are used to make decisions for the intensification of the field development process.
3. Samples from production wells are taken and analyzed 60–90 days in advance:
 - a) daily for the first 10–20 days;
 - b) every two days for 22–60 days;
 - c) every three days for 63–90 days.
4. According to the results of the analysis of the samples taken in each production well, plots of the dependence of the concentration of the labeled substance in the reservoir product on time from the beginning of injection are plotted.

On the basis of these results can be determined:

- density of hydrodynamic connection between injection and production wells;
- inter-formation cross-flow;
- tagged fluid filtration rate in the reservoir space;
- distribution of filtration flows in the reservoir space;
- permeability of the reservoir system where the tagged liquid is being filtered;

- the volume of reservoir medium, in which tagged liquid is being filtered;
- participation of injection fluid in the filtration process.
- extent of injecting fluid involvement in the watering of production of each produced well.
- impact on changes in reservoir filtration flows of measures to provide injectivity profiles of injection wells;
- efficiency of pumped liquid injection, etc.

Figure. Technology for detecting formation overflows of injected fluid of injection wells.

A distinctive feature of the presented method of detection of in-situ fluid flows of injection wells is that the injection fluid, prepared on the basis of an aqueous suspension of magnetic nanocomposite with spin-measured macro-heterocycle, is quickly recognized in the dark water-oil medium of the production of upstream wells at the analysis by the method of electro-vapor resonance (EPR) spectroscopy, as a result of which the resonance absorption of electromagnetic radiation by unpaired electrons of the composite is determined.

Besides, the water suspension used for the preparation of the injection fluid is made on the base of a magnetic powder with granularity a few orders of magnitude smaller than the size of the pore channels and has a grain size distribution within the range of $(5 < \mu < 10)$ nm, which is of advantage for prevention of plugging of the reservoir pore channels due to powder grain sedimentation and providing its flow in the inter-well space.

It should be noted that deviation of indicators at this method of inter-well space detection from the established framework values depends primarily on complications at various stages of preparation, injection of injected fluid, and analysis of production well results in projects on water flooding of the

productive horizon. The above complications of water flooding may be caused by:

- uneven distribution of the injected fluid in the space of the drained reservoir due to the heterogeneity of filtration characteristics in this volume of the reservoir;
- uneven remoteness of the injection well from the producing wells involved in the development of the pay zone;
- the presence of intensity variability within the reservoir cross-flow and its influence on the water flooding results (producing wells react with a lag).
- The impact of nearby wells in the development grid during the process of pressure maintenance on the water flooding process and occurrence of complications in the form of water encroachment of the producing wells, which leads to decrease in the well product output.

Conclusion

The treatment of the injection fluid with water suspension prepared on the basis of magnetic nano-composite containing spun macro-heterocycle gives it EPR activity, which allows detecting the inter-well space and determining the presence of the injection fluid in the production of the produced fluid. This, in its turn, confirms the existence of a communication channel between injection and production wells, which provides the flow of injection fluid.

Thus, the route map of inter-well pore space in the drained reservoir section is reconstructed, and it becomes possible to make corresponding corrections to the water flood projects under implementation aimed at reservoir pressure maintenance. It is very important for several operators during the implementation of development projects on the development of resources of one productive horizon for conflict solution related to, on one hand, attempts of one operator to maintain reservoir pressure by implementing water flood projects for the increase of production level and, on the other hand, the occurrence of well watering and increase of production level of another operator due to within reservoir injected fluid overflows in the process of water flood. Therefore, the possibility of detection of intraformational fluid overflows, injected through the injection wells, allows adjustment well flooding projects, implemented for drainage and improvement of filtration-capacitative characteristics of the given reservoir space.

The obtained information about the condition and the degree of drainage of the water-flooded reservoir is the base for determining more preferable location coordinates of additional injection wells. The correct location of injection wells in the field development grid will guarantee the required drillability within the reservoir space and reservoir pressure maintenance at the required area. Such correction of flooding projects will contribute to increase in the production level of producing wells and oil recovery of the productive horizon as a whole.

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